

KALMAN FILTER RESIDUAL EXPERT SYSTEM

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Abstract

The Pilot's Associate (PA) program has been initiated to help mitigate the extensive workload of the fighter pilot. To operate effectively, the PA system must have situation awareness: an integrated "feel" for the condition of on-board systems and the status and significance of external objects. Thus, the PA must continually monitor and evaluate important aircraft, weapon, and threat systems as well as terrain and weather conditions. The required information is gained through sensor systems. The data from these systems must be "fused" together to present the PA with a coherent picture of the environment. One common technique for fusing sensor data uses Kalman filters in a multiple model adaptive filter (MMAF).

We present an improved filter selection technique as part of an advanced MMAF. A knowledge-based system is used to augment the usual selection technique, and preliminary results indicate that this approach helps in situations that are known to cause problems for Kalman filter-based MMAF systems.

Historical Background.

The workload of the fighter pilot has been steadily increasing. Today's pilot is expected to keep track of a myriad of systems and sub-systems, checking them for anomalies, while simultaneously engaging a target and possibly evading a hostile threat. This workload will continue to increase as the next generation of fighter aircraft introduce new sensors to which the pilot must respond.

The information content of the sensor "subsystems" is steadily increasing through innovations such as active-element phased-array radar antennas, focal-plane array infrared sensors, on-board digital terrain and feature storage systems, high-sensitivity with high-angular accuracy anti-radiation sensors, improved navigation sensors and integrated communications systems [4,p.1330].

To alleviate the workload of future fighter pilots, the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) has created the Pilot's Associate (PA) Program. The specific purpose of this program is to demonstrate and evaluate the use of

artificial intelligence (AI) and expert systems for increasing the effectiveness of future combat aircraft. The kernel task of the PA system is the retrieval of available sensor data and the development of assessments based upon that data. Without this "real world" information, the system can neither suggest nor initiate logical actions.

Sensor Fusion.

A significant problem with perceiving the external state is the uncertainty associated with the sensed data. Sensors may be designed to provide various types of information about potential threats. Each sensor has its own strengths and weaknesses and thus supplies data with varying degrees of precision and accuracy. For instance, a laser rangefinder may provide excellent range data and relatively poor elevation and azimuth data. By combining data from various sources, using some type of sensor fusion process, complementary and competing interpretations can be combined to determine the most likely external state.

Three categories of techniques have been developed to address the fusion problem. The first uses AI techniques developed to facilitate reasoning under uncertainty (RUU). This technique uses processed data, possibly refined by Kalman filters. The second technique is a hybrid approach that attempts to address both the post-filter RUU techniques as well as the processing of the raw data that occurs within the filters. The last technique concentrates on the processes that go on within the Kalman filter system, using expert knowledge to make improvements in performance.

A fairly comprehensive review of current work in handling uncertainty in expert systems has been written by P.P. Bonissone [2]. He concludes that there are two basic approaches to representing uncertainty: numerical and symbolic characterizations [2,p.2]. Numerical approaches are characterized by values represented by a single number or an interval. An example of this approach is the Evidential Reasoning work done by Thomas Garvey, et. al., [5,p.319]. This technique is based upon the Dempster-Shafer theory [2,p.9] and lends itself to problems where the relationships and independence between variables can be fully described. The symbolic approach may be applicable when the information provided tends to be subjective or have imprecise relationships between variables [2,p.2]. An example of this type of approach is the work done by Steven Shafer, et.al., in developing a framework for sensor

fusion for an intelligent mobile robot [12]. Paul Cohen has also investigated the use of symbolic reasoning, developing a technique known as the Theory of Endorsements [3]. These techniques operate on post-processed sensor data and may be too slow for the rapid, real-time fighter aircraft environment.

The composite approach considers two aspects of sensor fusion. The first aspect is the pre-processed, MMAF fusion that occurs on the "sensor side." The second aspect is the post-processed, knowledge-based fusion that occurs on the "human side." Ronald Yannone [14] and Julius Reiner [11] have both proposed composite approach models. The quality of the post-processed fusion is dependent upon how well the MMAF fusion performs. The Air Force Wright Aeronautical Laboratories (AFWAL) is investigating various ways to perform this type of fusion.

Part of AFWAL's research is focusing on ways of applying artificial intelligence mechanisms to the airborne navigation problem domain. This includes the development of an expert system that chooses between combinations of navigation sensors that pass through Kalman filters [1,p.1]. This technique proved effective in the navigation-problem domain since sensors could be ranked a priori in terms of accuracy and precision. However, due to the nature of the tracking sensors, this type of pre-sorted Kalman filter selection criteria would not be appropriate for target tracking.

The remainder of this paper will present a more thorough overview of Kalman filters and the development of a new Kalman filter selection process. The new selection process augments the MMAF approach with a knowledge-based system that uses rules provided by a Kalman filter expert.

MMAF Sensor Fusion.

An operating MMAF system continually selects which filter to use as the basis for the state estimates. The overall accuracy of the system is closely related to how well the filters are selected. Previous filter selection techniques have proved useful, but limited.

The MMAF is usually comprised of two or more Kalman filters. A Kalman filter may be thought of as a recursive data processing algorithm. This filter is recursive in that it uses a feedback loop to compare its output, a state estimate, with the next input measurement [8,p.217]. A diagram of a simple Kalman filter is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Basic Kalman filter design [8,p.217].

The values K , H , B , and Φ are matrices that define the characteristics of the filter. The K matrix defines the filter's internal model. The H matrix defines the measurement model characteristics. The B and Φ matrices identify the dynamics model parameters. The process of adjusting the K matrix so the filter responds to certain changes in the input is known as tuning. The measurement $z(t_i)$ is the input at time t_i . The value $\hat{z}(t_i^-)$ is the filter's best prediction of the actual measurement $z(t_i)$. This prediction is computed by the filter at time t_i^- . The difference between the actual measurement and the predicted measurement is known as the residual and is identified as $r(t_i)$. The residual "...is then passed through an optimal weighting matrix K , and used to correct $\hat{x}(t_i^-)$, the best prediction of the state at time instant t_i , before the measurement is taken at time t_i ," [10]. For a full explanation of the filter and associated notation, see [8] and [9]. The residual may be likened to an error signal, although strictly it is not since the original measurement, $z(t_i)$, has uncertainty associated with it.

The magnitudes of the residuals are related to how well the matrices model the characteristics of events in the real-world. For example, two filters could be developed to track a target from radar data. One filter could be tuned for targets moving at constant velocity while the other could be tuned for targets characterized by constant acceleration. If the target did indeed travel at constant acceleration, the "goodness" of the corresponding filter should be indicated by the relatively low residuals during its updates. The filter having the less appropriate set of assumptions (i.e., that the target would have a constant velocity) is expected to have larger residual values.

Filters could also be developed to combine data from different types of sensors, each weighing such factors as individual sensor reliability and precision and the believed accuracy of the filter model. While sets of single-sensor filters could be developed, the standard implementation is to develop one set of filters having access to all related sensor data [10]. Allowing more than one sensor access to the Kalman filters provides a mechanism for sensor fusion.

Problems with current selection criterion.

In a multiple-filter system, each filter develops its own best estimate of the desired variable (e.g., target location) as well as a residual associated with that estimate. An example of this type of system is shown in Figure 2. The final state estimate provided by the multiple-filter system is based upon a weighted addition of the individual filter estimates. This weighting function is actually a conditional probability derived from a Bayesian estimation of the residuals [9, Sec.10]. This Bayesian estimation is the conditional probability that the parameter value produced by each filter is in fact the best estimate available, based upon that filter's residual values up to that time. This value, known as the residual's hypothesis conditional probability, shall be referred to as the residual's probability. The sum of these probabilities across all filters equals one. The final weighted estimate is referred to as the Bayesian estimate.

Figure 2: Multiple model filtering algorithm [9, p.123].

An alternative approach to weighting the multiple Kalman filter estimates is to select the estimate from the filter with the largest residual probability. This technique is known as maximum a posteriori (MAP) state estimation [7,p.20]. As an example, assume filters A and B have residual probabilities of 0.6 and 0.4, respectively. Instead of computing a weighted average of the filter state estimates ($0.6 \hat{a} + 0.4 \hat{b}$), just select filter A's estimate ($\hat{a}$). A Monte Carlo simulation comparison of the Bayesian and MAP estimates show that, at least for the Kalman filter models and target trajectories used, the techniques resulted in very similar performance [7,p.83]. The MAP estimate technique will be the one considered throughout the remainder of this report.

Dr. Peter Maybeck [10] has identified two problems that can occur when selecting the best filter to use in a multiple-filter system. (The "better" and "best" filters are those deemed that way by the expert.) The first problem he identified was a tendency for certain filters to "hold on" to the system longer than they should. Because of this, there can be a delay in switching to a better filter. The second problem he identified could occur when a new filter needed to be selected. Under certain situations, the filter with the new highest residual probability may not be the correct one to choose. Dr. Maybeck anticipated that he and other filter designers could do a better job at selecting filters than the original system.

Proposed filter selection criteria.

To arrive at a solution, an expert must use information relevant to the problem. The information provided by Kalman filters (i.e., the raw residual data) is not in an appropriate format for an expert to select a filter. An example of raw residual data is shown in Figure 3. Each filter produces X and Y residuals which correspond to the X and Y target location estimates developed by that filter. (X and Y refer here to the target's apparent azimuth and elevation from the ground-based sensor's point of view.) The question then became, "How can

the data be processed so that the expert can make a decision?" Two data processing techniques were investigated. The first technique used statistical information concerning the residuals while the second used the residual probability data.

We computed several statistics on the raw data, including mean and Gaussianity tests, etc., and then attempted to formulate rules with the results. We were not successful with this approach. More information on the actual statistics computed and the resulting plots are available in [6].

The alternative selection criterion was to base expert rules on the residual probability data. An example of the residual probabilities developed by an MMAF simulation is shown in Figure 4. The abscissa of this figure runs from zero to eight seconds (with marks every half second), while the ordinate runs from zero to one. The figure shows the five filter residual probabilities superimposed on each other with numbers provided to differentiate between the probability curves.

Figure 3: Kalman filter number one residual data from trajectory two.

Figure 4: Residual probabilities from trajectory two.

The current technique, MAP, selects the filter with the highest probability. Thus, in Figure 4, MAP would first select filter number one until just after one second at which time it would switch to filter number four. This would then continue for the entire trajectory.

To test the residual probability-based approach, we modified an existing MMAF simulation so that it recorded the results of the standard MAP selection process. Based on this information, the expert developed filter selection rules using his knowledge of the trajectory and Kalman filter characteristics. The resulting rule-based system then analyzed the residual data and recorded its own filter selections. A side-by-side comparison between the original MAP and the new knowledge-based techniques allowed Dr. Maybeck to evaluate and occasionally modify the expert rules. Since the expert could develop rules based on the residual probability data, this became the basis for the expert system.

Figure 5 shows the organization of the various software components. A more complete description of the simulator and the rule-based system follows.

Figure 5: Software system block diagram.

Kalman filter simulation.

The goal of the original Kalman filter program was to address the problem of accurately tracking the azimuth and elevation of a highly maneuverable airborne target, using outputs from a forward-looking infrared (FLIR) sensor as measurements [13,p.1].

To do this, the program simulates five Kalman filters receiving data from a single sensor. The filters are tuned for different models of targets. For example, filter one is tuned for a benign target, while filter two is tuned for a harshly maneuvering target. Characteristics of these filters are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Simulated Kalman Filter Characteristics.

Filter Number	Field of View (az x el)	Target Acceleration Model	Target Model
1	8x8	0-g	benign
2	24x24	20-g	harsh maneuver
3	8x8	10-g	smooth maneuver
4	24x8	20-g (az)	azimuthal maneuver
5	8x24	20-g (el)	elevational maneuver

At each interval during the simulation, the five filters develop independent state estimates of the target based upon the simulated FLIR sensor data. The goal of the expert system is to select the filter with the best estimate.

Ten simulated trajectories were used to stress the original MAP filter selection process. Based upon these results, the expert was able to develop rules that selected better filters.

KREST.

The Kalman Residual Expert System (KREST) could have been developed using a conventional programming language, but instead, an AI framework was selected to expedite the adding and refining of knowledge. This knowledge took the form of "If - Then" constructs so a rule-based expert system shell was selected. The shell chosen was OPS-5.

In general, the MAP selection process performs well. However, problems can occur when the residual probability of the selected filter is decreasing while that of another filter is increasing. Sometimes filters are slow to respond to changes in target motion. This is especially true of the harsh trajectory filters when the target trajectory becomes benign. Another problem can occur during transitions between orthogonal filters. During these occurrences, the expert felt that instead of switching directly from a horizontal filter to a vertical one (or vice versa) that the system should first transition to a square filter before selecting the orthogonal one.

The expert system filter selections for portions of some of the trajectories are shown in Tables 3 and 5. In these tables: Time is the specific time interval; Rule is the number of the KREST rule that fired, if any; KF is the filter KREST selected; MAP is the filter selected by the maximum a

posteriori selection process (the filter with the largest residual probability); and P1 through P5 are the residual probabilities of filters one through five, respectively.

Tendency toward more benign filters.

Rules 30 and 55 (Table 2) are examples of KREST rules developed to compensate for the original system's tendency to adhere to non-benign filters. These rules select filter three when the residual probabilities of filters two and three met certain constraints. (Note: The precondition Best=2 in Rule 50 is satisfied when the residual probability of filter two is larger than all others. The precondition Best=3 for last 3 or more is satisfied when KREST has selected filter three during the previous three time intervals.) Table 3 demonstrates that these rules make the system tend toward the narrow field of view (FOV), more benign filters. While the original system occasionally selects filter two following time 119, KREST sticks with filter three based upon the significant residual probability of that filter. Balanced with the desire for improved tracking resolution is the need to keep track of target. Thus, while this type of rule "encourages" the use of narrow FOV/benign filters, it does not overly restrict the system when the use of a wider FOV filter is indicated. The thresholds were set in Rules 30 and 55 to achieve this balance.

Table 2. KREST Rules 30 and 55.

Rule	Precondition	Filter
30	If Best=3 for last 3 or more and the new Best=2 and P2 < 0.7 and P3 > 0.2	3
55	If Best=2 and P3 > 0.25	3

Smoother filter transitions.

The purpose of KREST Rule 70 (see Table 4) was to provide for a smoother transition between the orthogonal filters four (X-oriented) and five (Y-oriented). The expert determined that if both of these filters have significant residual probability values, the best choice would be one of the square FOV filters. Specifically, the system should select either filter one with its narrow, square FOV or filter two with its large, square FOV. Rules 70 and 75 were developed with similar preconditions, the difference being that Rule 70 selects filter one and Rule 75 selects filter two. The filter with the higher residual probability determines which of these two rules fires. An example of KREST's use of this type of rule is shown in Table 5. Whereas the original system transitioned directly from filter five to filter four at time 162 and back to filter five at time 165, KREST provided a smoother transition by using filter one.

Table 3. KREST Results for a Portion of Trajectory Two.

Time	Rule	KF	MAP	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5
116		1	1	0.781	0.101	0.092	0.001	0.025
117		1	1	0.721	0.123	0.126	0.001	0.029
118		2	2	0.213	0.580	0.179	0.004	0.025
119		2	2	0.243	0.522	0.211	0.004	0.021
120	55	3	2	0.165	0.438	0.370	0.003	0.024
121	55	3	2	0.057	0.524	0.408	0.002	0.009
122	55	3	2	0.045	0.499	0.446	0.002	0.007
123		3	3	0.193	0.066	0.712	0.008	0.021
124		3	3	0.190	0.046	0.737	0.007	0.019
125		3	3	0.098	0.067	0.815	0.014	0.006
126		3	3	0.052	0.063	0.867	0.015	0.004
127		3	3	0.086	0.106	0.783	0.018	0.007
128		3	3	0.018	0.270	0.695	0.014	0.003
129		3	3	0.006	0.399	0.582	0.008	0.004
130		3	3	0.006	0.365	0.620	0.007	0.002
131		3	3	0.003	0.470	0.520	0.006	0.002
132	30	3	2	0.001	0.575	0.419	0.001	0.004
133		3	3	0.002	0.263	0.730	0.003	0.002
134		3	3	0.001	0.250	0.748	0.001	0.001
135		3	3	0.001	0.213	0.784	0.001	0.001
136		3	3	0.001	0.241	0.755	0.001	0.001
137		3	3	0.001	0.190	0.807	0.001	0.001
138		3	3	0.001	0.173	0.824	0.001	0.001
139		3	3	0.001	0.383	0.613	0.001	0.001
140		3	3	0.001	0.467	0.530	0.001	0.001
141	30	3	2	0.001	0.651	0.346	0.002	0.001
142	30	3	2	0.001	0.546	0.450	0.001	0.001
143	30	3	2	0.002	0.519	0.477	0.001	0.002
144		3	3	0.001	0.458	0.538	0.001	0.001
145		3	3	0.001	0.463	0.533	0.001	0.001
146		3	3	0.001	0.427	0.570	0.001	0.001
147		3	3	0.001	0.405	0.592	0.001	0.001
148	30	3	2	0.001	0.529	0.468	0.001	0.001
149		3	3	0.001	0.460	0.536	0.001	0.001
150		3	3	0.001	0.061	0.935	0.002	0.001
151		3	3	0.002	0.027	0.966	0.004	0.001

Table 4. KREST Rules 70 and 75.

Rule	Precondition	Selected Filter
70	If Best=4 or 5 and P4 < 0.6 and P5 < 0.6 and P3 < 0.2 and P1 > 0.1 and P1 > P2	1
75	If Best=4 or 5 and P4 < 0.6 and P5 < 0.6 and P3 < 0.2 and P2 > 0.1 and P2 > P1	2

Table 5. KREST Results for a Portion of Trajectory Three.

Time	Rule	KF	MAP	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5
151		5	5	0.136	0.001	0.017	0.054	0.791
152	-	5	5	0.038	0.034	0.011	0.353	0.564
153	-	5	5	0.048	0.025	0.012	0.338	0.577
154	-	5	5	0.051	0.008	0.010	0.369	0.562
155	-	5	5	0.061	0.006	0.009	0.392	0.532
156		5	5	0.058	0.005	0.010	0.254	0.673
157		5	5	0.034	0.005	0.008	0.165	0.787
158		5	5	0.038	0.005	0.008	0.150	0.800
159		5	5	0.038	0.004	0.007	0.127	0.824
160	70	1	5	0.128	0.001	0.011	0.346	0.514
161	70	1	5	0.141	0.001	0.008	0.344	0.506
162		4	4	0.021	0.029	0.007	0.856	0.086
163		4	4	0.032	0.013	0.010	0.834	0.112
164	70	1	4	0.125	0.019	0.018	0.481	0.357
165	70	1	5	0.174	0.004	0.014	0.282	0.526
166	70	1	5	0.212	0.003	0.015	0.297	0.473
167	70	1	5	0.186	0.003	0.014	0.308	0.490
168	70	1	5	0.195	0.003	0.029	0.336	0.437
169	70	1	5	0.189	0.002	0.030	0.372	0.406
170	70	1	5	0.217	0.002	0.030	0.362	0.389
171		3	3	0.123	0.005	0.507	0.173	0.192
172	40	1	3	0.287	0.001	0.355	0.098	0.259
173		1	1	0.402	0.001	0.294	0.066	0.237
174		1	1	0.488	0.001	0.203	0.062	0.245
175		1	1	0.550	0.001	0.160	0.054	0.236

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Conclusions.

By analyzing the residual probability graphs of the five simulated Kalman filters, the expert (Dr. Maybeck) was able to express rules that selected the filters he desired. The resulting expert system, KREST, provided an improvement over the original MAP selection process. Although no quantitative estimate of improvement is available, Dr. Maybeck stated that KREST exhibited a "...potentially very significant performance improvement over the Bayesian and MAP filter selection techniques" [10]. The encouraging performance of KREST indicates that advanced MMAF systems infused with some type of expert knowledge, may help lessen the problems associated with sensor data fusion.

Future Work.

There are several ways this research could be extended. These include embedding the rules from the expert system into the original simulation software and modifying the multiple model adaptive filters to simulate sensor fusion. The next step, however, should probably be to numerically evaluate the KREST filter selection process. The KREST and MAP selected filters should be compared against the filter whose estimate is closest to that of the simulated target. In addition to providing a mechanism to objectively evaluate KREST, this information could be used to further refine the KREST rules.

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